

Open Science Commission: 2019 achievements

Executive summary

Adoption of dataverse and creation of a Data Management Plans (DMP) single point of reference

2019 was an important year for the implementation of Dataverse (Dataverse.unimi.it), the tool chosen by the university to support Research data management policy. At the same time, Data Management Plan models were developed and made available to Principal investigators.

Migration of the OJS epublishing platform to the new version OJS3

In the second part of 2019 all the editors of the platform riviste.unimi.it were involved and engaged in testing activities for the transition to the new platform, which ended in November with the opening of a new interface with a renewed homepage. One million downloads in a year were registered in December and so a milestone was reached.

Monitoring of open access in the Departments

Monitoring activities on the percentage of open access publications continued throughout the year and led to very satisfactory results. It worth mentioning that the University has set, in its new strategic plan, the ambitious target of reaching 50% of open access publications in the period 2020-2022.

Project Open APC

At the beginning of 2019, clear and accurate indications were provided to the Departments to ensure a more appropriate recording of APC. However, the AIR group continued to collect information on APCs directly from the authors in order to validate the accounting data.

Post grant FP7

The results of the FP7 post grant have been published, an activity in which the AIR Support Office and the Research office have been engaged for a couple of years (since 2016). The data shows excellent results for the University of Milan, which has been amongst the major beneficiaries of the post grant initiative.